

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF OXIDES IN THE $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{O-TiO}_2\text{-K}_2\text{O-B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-P}_2\text{O}_5$ SYSTEM ON THE DULLNESS OF THE ENAMEL COATING.

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To cover the dark color of the ground enamel, the enamel coatings should be matte – muted. Haze is the process of turning transparent enamel into opaque due to refraction, reflection and diffraction of light[1].

The more the enamel is suppressed, i.e. characterized by high covering power, the more this affects the technical and operational properties of the coating. It is known that with an enamel layer thickness of 0.3-0.5 mm, enameled products can be subjected to significant deformations and sudden temperature changes without fear of compromising the integrity of the enamel coating. When the thickness of the enamel layer is about 1 mm, slight deformation of the product or its sudden heating causes chipping of the enamel [2–3].

Also, the aesthetic appearance of the product depends on the dullness of the enamel coatings, that is, the more dulled the enamel, the more beautiful the appearance of the coating. Thus, suppression, in particular crystal suppression, plays an important role in the technology of enameling household products[4].

Conventional silicate glasses have an average refractive index of $n=1.52$. For jamming to be effective, the refractive index of the jammer must be either greater than 1.8 or less than 1.4. In this case, it does not matter which of the phases it is greater, the difference is important. Research [5–7] has identified a number of substances whose refractive index satisfies the requirements.

The synthesis of glasses for coating enamels was carried out in laboratory conditions. The basis was the $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{O-TiO}_2\text{-K}_2\text{O-B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-P}_2\text{O}_5$ system. The following raw materials were used for the synthesis of coating enamels; Quartz sand, limestone, soda ash, shale, boric acid, titanium oxide, potash and ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate. The chemical composition of the raw materials is presented in Table 1.

Table No. 1

Chemical composition of synthesized glasses

Composition No.	Chemical composition, mass %								
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	Fe ₂ O ₃	B ₂ O ₃
Nº1001	42,4	4,54	14,0	2,29	0,07	17,3	2,30	0,06	16,4
Nº1002	42,1	4,20	13,0	2,06	0,08	18,2	1,9	0,07	18,4
Nº1005	41,7	4,98	13,3	2,35	0,09	18,6	2,04	0,06	16,1
Nº1006	41,6	4,7	13,9	2,38	0,08	16,1	2,20	0,06	18,1
Nº1008	42,6	4,75	14,0	2,41	0,08	17,2	2,15	0,05	16,76
Nº1009	44,0	4,90	13,6	2,29	0,09	14,7	2,35	0,06	18,0

The frit was cooked in a laboratory oven heated using natural gas at a temperature of 1350°C for 1 hour. The melt was poured into water and frit granules were obtained. The physicochemical properties of enamel coatings are given in Table No. 2

Table No. 2

Physico-chemical properties of enamel coatings

Compositi on No.	Refractive index, n	Whiteness index, %	Acid-resistant,	Surface tension, H/m10 ⁻³
Nº1001	1,586	77,8	AA	2,39
Nº1002	1,605	80,5	AA	2,34
Nº1005	1,585	75,8	AA	2,48
Nº1006	1,571	69,5	AA	2,35
Nº1008	1,552	77,5	AA	2,39
Nº1009	1,577	68,1	A	2,37

When titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is included in the enamel coating, it changes the properties of the enamel depending on its charge number, in which titanium dioxide can be 4- or 6-coordinated. Due to the coordination state of Ti+4 ions, titanium dioxide acts as a suffocator in small alkaline compounds, so the dioxide tries to keep titanium in the Ti+6 coordination state, which reacts to form rutile or anatase. However, in conditions where the glass contains a lot of alkali, titanium dioxide acts as a stabilizer. The binding of ions in enamel depends on the energy of the glass structural lattice, the strength of the bond of cations with oxygen, and the strength of the cation field. The Ti-O bond is important and approaches the strength of the Si-O bond. To ensure communication between the Si-O-Si and Ti-O-Ti systems, one Na₂O (K₂O) molecule must correspond to one TiO₂ molecule[8].

In the process of analyzing Tables 1 and 2, it was established that: titanium dioxide acts as the main muffler, the necessary additives are introduced into the synthesized glass frit and applied to the surface of the primed metal, and during combustion at a temperature of 820–830 °C titanium dioxide exhibits high crystallinity and exhibits properties quenching due to the formation of anatase and rutile. Using sample No. 1005, it was found that increasing the amount of titanium dioxide has a positive effect on the crystallization process.

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